

The Meaning of Office Things: A Study of Special Objects in Office Environments

Sally Augustin, PlaceCoach, Inc. - USA

Abstract

This descriptive exploratory project investigated people's relationship to special office possessions. Building on the work of Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981), it probed associations between self-concept, types of possessions valued, the reasons possessions are valued, and emotional state experienced by workers. Participant emotional experiences were of particular interest because positive affect has been linked to broadened thinking patterns and expanded behavioral repertoires, higher levels of creativity, and other desired aspects of knowledge work (Isen, 2001). No significant relationships were found between either the types of special objects named or the reasons that objects were special and either job satisfaction or organizational commitment, when job satisfaction and organizational commitment were used as proxies for affect. Relationships were observed, however, between positive affect, as determined via the content analysis of interview conversations, and the presence of individually perceived special objects in the workplace. One hundred and fifty-five professionals completed written surveys in conjunction with this project; 16 of these individuals were also interviewed.

Keywords: Affective design, Special objects, Design, Emotion, Written surveys, Interviews, Workplace design

Introduction

A tool to evaluate workplace affect through analysis of special objects in offices would be useful. It would be more difficult for employees to answer such a series of questions in a socially desirable manner (Gagliardi, 1996), for example, than the scales currently used to assess workplace affect. The initial objective of this study was to begin to lay the foundation for the development of a special object based affect measurement tool, building on the work of Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981). Positive affect has been linked to many attributes and behaviors desired among knowledge workers, such as creativity and prosocial behavior (Isen, 2001).

This study conceptually replicates Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton's study of special possessions in residential environments, described in *The Meaning of Things* (1981), but focuses on special objects in office environments. Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton used the term "special" in their study because they felt the term allowed study participants to define the value of particular objects in whatever manner was individually appropriate. They gathered data through face-to-face interviews in the homes of their 315 participants. Their work and related work in home and office environments indicates that valued objects have complex and important effects at the individual and group levels, particularly in the symbolic communication related to the generation and support of the self-concept (Becker, 1982; Belk, 1988; Kamptner, 1991; Dittmar, 1992; Lunt and Livingstone, 1992; Richins, 1994; Marcus, 1995; Nippert-Eng, 1996; Gorowara-Bhat, 2000; Wilson and McKenzie, 2000).

The self is "made up of information about goals and feedback" (Csikszentmihalyi, 1993, p. 236) and an individual's self-concept has three primary components: social type or social identity, personal dispositions, and physical characteristics (Rosenberg, 1986). An individual has several self-concepts in place, varying by setting and level of idealization (Erez and Earley, 1993). All of the "language" through which material objects symbolically communicate is socially constructed through symbolic interaction, as described by Berger and Luckmann (1967) and by Mead (Blumer, 1969). Material objects have a special symbolic value because they are in most cases relatively permanent and also have a concrete form visible to others (McCarthy, 1984), although it may be difficult for anyone beside their owner to fully understand their meaning (Schein, 1992).

Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981) found distinct patterns of valued possessions among people expressing higher positive affect as compared to people with lower positive affect, with a generally diminished attachment to material possessions among people with higher positive affect. They also found a significantly higher number of times that objects were valued because of interpersonal connotations by people with more positive affect, as compared to individuals with less positive affect. These researchers assessed positive affect through content analysis of interview data.

Objects have been studied in office contexts largely because of their role in workspace personalization (“the deliberate adornment, decoration, modification, or rearrangement of an environment by its occupants to reflect their individual identities” (Sommer, 1974, p. 111)). Personalization of workspaces makes them comfortable to the personalizers and reinforces self-concept (Horne, 1997). People have a strong psychological need to personalize their workspaces (Wells, 2000).

Workspace personalization has been linked to job satisfaction and organizational commitment, although no measurement tools to formally relate these concepts have been developed. Wells (2000) demonstrated that employees who personalize their workspaces are more satisfied with their jobs and workplaces and experience higher personal and organizational well-being. BOSTI (1984) surveyed office workers and determined that office personalization and job satisfaction were positively related. Scheiberg (1992) saw office personalizations as indicating one’s level of commitment to an organization. Individuals who are committed to an organization may personalize related places more (Hansen and Altman, 1976) and in more organizationally relevant ways (Vinsel et al., 1980) than less committed individuals. Objects that an individual has used to personalize an office are clearly of interest to that individual, but these items might not be the special office objects, which that person relates to their self-concept. Office objects assigned by the employer might have a more significant impact on perceived self-concept, in some cases.

Fredrickson defines affect as “Present within emotions (as the component of subjective experience), it is also present within many other affective phenomena, including physical sensations, attitudes, moods, and even affective traits” (2001, p. 218). Others have used the term “affect” to refer to both mood and emotion (James, Brodersen, and Eisenberg, 2004). This more general definition of “affect” is used here. Positive affect is usually defined as

“pleasant feelings induced by commonplace events or circumstances” (Isen and Baron, 1991, p. 1) and the definition for negative affect is generally the reverse (Thoresen, Kaplan, Barsky, and Warren, 2003).

Positive affect has been linked to several specific outcomes; please refer to Table 1 for a representative list.

Table 1: Outcomes Linked to Positive Affect

Broadened thinking/attention and thought-action repertoires, when compared to neutral or negative state processing (Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005).
Improved creative performance and increased innovation (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, and Robinson, 1985)
Improved problem solving and decision making (Isen, 2001)
More flexible, thorough, and efficient thinking on topics meaningful or interesting to the thinker (Isen, 2001)
Strategic thinking (Loken, 2006)
Constructive and cooperative bargaining, increased generosity, social responsibility, helping and interpersonal understanding (Isen, 2001)
Constructive suggestions (George and Brief, 1992)
Avoidance of real and meaningful risk (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, and Robinson, 1985)
Increased halo errors (Isen and Baron, 1991)
Improved self-knowledge (Frederickson, 2001).

Positive emotions can help build durable personal resources such as physical skills or health, social resources such as friendships and networks, intellectual resources such as knowledge, and psychological resources such as optimism (Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005). Early research indicated that positive affect might lead to decreased cognitive capacity or motivation to process information systematically, but more recent evidence has indicated the opposite effect (Isen, 2001).

Negative affect also clearly relates to knowledge worker behavior. In addition to not exhibiting the linkages noted above for positive affect, it encourages thorough, analytical, detail-oriented, systematic thinking, but in more focused areas and narrower thought-action repertoires than in a neutral state (Cote, 1999; Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005). Brief and Weiss (2002) report that negative affect in the workplace has been linked to negative interpersonal interactions, anxiety, more extreme emotions after negative work experiences, and reduced positive response to positive workplace events. Negative affect and positive affect are not necessarily related to inverse patterns of mental processing, behaviors, etc. (Isen and Baron, 1991).

Affect can be environmentally induced. For example, positive affect can be generated through environmental factors, such as smells (Baron, 1990). Baron found that individuals experiencing a pleasant scent exhibited behaviors consistent with positive affect (Baron, 1990). There are many other demonstrations of environmentally induced positive affect in the literature related not only to smells, but also to social density, lighting levels, level of enclosure, and interpersonal distancing, for example (Isen and Baron, 1991).

Higher levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment have generally been positively linked to positive affect; and job satisfaction and organizational commitment are studied extensively in the organizational literature. Thoresen, Kaplan, Barsky, and Warren (2003) completed a meta-analysis and determined that both trait and state positive affect were positively correlated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment and that state and trait negative affect were negatively correlated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Thoresen et al.'s definition of job satisfaction is drawn from Locke (1976, p. 1300), "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences" while their definition of organizational commitment ("an employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization" (Thoresen et al., 2003, p. 917)) is drawn from Hackett et al (1994). Trait positive or negative affect refers to a tendency to experience positively or negatively activated emotions, respectively (Thoresen et al., 2003). State affect is seen as what a person is feeling at a particular moment (Thoresen et al., 2003). Job satisfaction and job performance appear to be positively related while job satisfaction is inversely related to turnover and absenteeism (Cote, 1999). Several studies have indicated that components of the physical environment influence job satisfaction

(Sundstrom, 1986). Organizational commitment has been positively related to length of employment with a firm (Johns, 1996).

This research explored the relationships between office objects selected as special and employee affect. People higher in job satisfaction and organizational commitment were expected to be more likely to value possessions because they indicated an interpersonal connection of some sort. Also, less attachment to material possessions was expected among more satisfied and committed workers, based on Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton's (1981) observations relating affect and valued objects. No published studies have linked organizational commitment or job satisfaction and valued office objects.

Methodology

Written questionnaires and oral interviews were used to collect information. One hundred and fifty-five individuals participated in this study. Sixteen of the professionals who completed written questionnaires were also randomly selected and interviewed to contextualize the responses received to the written questions. These 16 individuals were shown via t-tests to be statistically indistinguishable from respondents who completed only the survey instrument, based on comparisons of participants' selection of types of objects valued and reasons objects were valued, and job satisfaction and organizational commitment scale scores.

An office was defined as the work area provided by a firm to an employee at a corporate facility not in a manufacturing setting. Home offices were not considered in this study. Office objects were defined as components of the office environment that are not permanent features of the building in which the workspace is located.

Data were collected from professionals employed by organizations. Professionals were defined as individuals who work in office environments but do not do maintenance work or related support tasks. Professionals were selected as the sample group because they experience the environment in different ways than support workers (BOSTI, 1984).

Respondents were asked to complete the survey in their offices and were provided with a stamped envelope to return the survey. Two hundred and fifty copies of the survey were

distributed, with a 62% response rate. Four additional surveys could not be included in analyses because errors were made in responding to questions posed on the survey.

The basic questions which Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981) used as the backbone of their interview guide directed this research. The sections of the survey relevant to this paper are described here. Individuals were asked to name 5 possessions in their office that were special to them and the reasons they were valued in open-ended questions, with the single most special object listed first. Participants then described objects in their offices that they found undesirable and indicated why these objects were objectionable. A standard measure of job satisfaction (Job in General Scale) (Balzar, Kihm, Smith, Irwin, Bachiochi, Robie, Sinar, and Parra, 1997), a measure of organizational commitment (Mowday, Porter, and Steers, 1982), several demographic questions, and queries about the physical workspace assigned to the participant completed the questionnaire. The survey was pretested and performed appropriately.

The coding scheme for the qualitative data was developed after repeated readings of the data revealed patterns in the material and after consideration of the topics raised in the literature review, particularly in Dittmar, 1989. Objects selected as special were coded as: practical, specialty indicator (individuating symbol), sentimental (arising from a past situation), providing pleasure directly (e.g., due to their design), or other. The reasons that objects were selected as special were coded as: use, embodiment of relationship with others, personal description (e.g., symbols of a particular ability), physical feature of the object, enjoyment, emotional support, lifespan chronicle, status, or other. To facilitate statistical analyses, the raw counts of object types and reasons selected as special were converted to percentages, in a manner similar to that used in Dittmar, 1989. For the analysis of the types of objects listed as special, the percent of responses provided in each category were determined for each participant, with the total percent of responses coded totaling 100% for each person. Similarly, the relative frequency of each reason why an object might be selected as special was calculated for each participant. This sort of manipulation was particularly important for this variable, because some individuals gave multiple reasons why an object was special to them, while others gave only single reasons. Apparent level of attachment to material possessions was coded as low, medium, or high.

High kappa scores between the coders (.89 for object selected as special, .91 for reason objects selected as special, .85 for apparent level of attachment to possessions) indicated that the coding system had an acceptable level of reliability (Cohen, 1960).

Results

Descriptive analyses of the data collected were completed. Forty-two men and 113 women from across the United States completed the survey; data from a total of 155 people were analyzed. The mean age of respondents was 45. On average, individuals had been in their current job function for 12 years, working for their current employer for 7 years, and spent 37 hours a week in their workspaces. Seventy-two percent had no restrictions on materials they could place in their workspaces. Professionally, 12% of respondents had marketing/sales jobs and 20% were in general management, other individuals surveyed had professions such as counselors/therapists, accountants, or operations specialists. Forty percent were in middle management, 34% were in junior management, and 25% were in senior management. Twenty-eight percent of respondents worked at nonprofit organizations, 13% worked at healthcare organizations, and 12% worked in education.

Scores on all of the standardized scales administered to study participants were consistent with the values of these scales seen in similar samples. The median score on the measure of job satisfaction was 46 (possible range 0-54) and the median score on the organizational commitment scale was 5.54 (possible range 1-7). The mean of the job satisfaction score was 43, while the mean of the organizational commitment score was 5.2. When the job satisfaction scale is administered to employees in for-profit organizations, 33% of scores are usually in the 37-45 range, while 31% are higher and 35% lower (Balzar, et al., 1997). The mean scores across many groups tested on the organizational commitment scale have ranged from 4.2 to 5.3 (Mowday, Porter, and Steers, 1982). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment have generally been found to be positively correlated in past research and a similar relationship was found here ($r=.725, p<.001$).

Photos, usually of family members or close friends, were selected as the most special object in their workspace by 31% of the respondents, while artwork, usually by family members or close friends, was selected as the most special object in the workplace by 15% of participants. Computers were selected as the most valued workplace object by 17% of participants, the

desk chair was selected as their most special object by 5% of respondents, the desk itself was the first-listed special object by 3% of participants, and the phone was selected as most special object by 3% of participants.

T-tests were used to compare the special possession choices (types of objects and reasons special) of people high and low in job satisfaction (above or below median score) and high and low in organizational commitment (above or below median score). No statistically significant relationships were found. Across the entire sample and within each population segmentation studied, practical objects were most likely to be valued followed by specialty indicators, and sentimental objects. Again, across the entire sample and within each population segmentation studied, the most frequently cited reason an object was viewed as special was use, followed by embodiment of relationship with others, with the third most frequently listed reason for valuing a special object being personal description.

When data from all participants was analyzed via MANOVA, individuals with levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment above and below the median values on these scales did not value different objects (job satisfaction: Pillai's Trace=.016, $F(5, 149) = .48$, p n.s.; organizational commitment: Pillai's Trace=.065, $F(5, 149) = 2.064$, p n.s.). Analyzing reasons objects were valued via MANOVA did not show significant differences by levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment (job satisfaction: Pillai's Trace=.032, $F(8, 146) = .605$, p n.s.; organizational commitment: Pillai's Trace=.019, $F(8, 146) = .36$, p n.s.). Pillai's Trace is reported because it is more robust than alternative reporting options (Tabachnick and Fidell, 1996).

Apparent level of attachment to possessions did not correlate significantly with job satisfaction ($r = .031$, $p = \text{n.s.}$) or organizational commitment ($r = .074$, $p = \text{n.s.}$).

Fewer than 5% of those surveyed explicitly described psychological discomfort with objects in their workplace. Forty percent of individuals indicated through their survey responses that there were items in their work area that were inconsistent with their self-concept. Although the researcher was presented as independent of the employer, participants may have felt that voicing unhappiness with objects placed in their workplace could have negative professional results.

During their interviews, participants revealed intricacies of their relationships with the special objects in their workspaces that were not clearly presented in the written responses to survey questions. Special objects represented individual workplace self-concepts and their presence was heavily tied to emotional well-being and positive affect in the workplace, as described by the interviewees and content analyzed by the researcher. Affect expressed was categorized as positive or negative using cues such as the adjectives incorporated into the PANAS Scale (Watson, Clark, and Tellegen, 1988) and the Job Affect Scale (Burke et. al, 1989).

Positive affect was present when interviewees considered or interacted with the special objects in their workplaces. Negative affect resulted from consideration of or interaction with objects inconsistent with the interviewee's self-concept that were present in the workplace.

Interviewees moved special objects to new jobs when they changed jobs. Special objects were placed to maximize the interviewee's interaction with these objects. All of the special objects discussed by interviewees were positioned in plain view in workspaces and they were placed so that they were viewable by the interviewee while sitting in their workspace. Interviewees regularly stated that "Looking at (etc.) [special object named] makes me feel good." The individuals interviewed took advantage of whatever space was available to them to present their special objects.

Several reasons why objects were viewed as special were mentioned by interviewees. The interviewees as a group used their special objects as a way to remind themselves of who they were as well as to inform people visiting their workspaces about whom they felt themselves to be. Comments by interviewees that an object was special because he/she didn't want to forget "where I come from" indicate that special objects can be self preservation tools. This self preservation, like the self projection, resulted in positive affect. In general, the special objects identified related to past or present conditions, as opposed to future goals.

Individuals valued objects that related to them individually, no group owned objects were selected as special. People valued objects based on their own perceptions of themselves; other people had little overt influence on the collection of objects viewed as special. Objects selected as special did not seem to be related to organizational culture in a direct way. The set of objects selected as special was often apparently independent of the context of a

particular organizational culture or set of professional responsibilities. They might be a performance reward, however, or an object that could be valued by other members in their firm, indicating some sorts of shared social concepts related to valued objects.

Individuals interviewed clearly took pride in the objects that they selected as special and were very concerned that the proper objects be recognized as special. In order to make it clear to the researcher which objects were special, many interviewees walked around their workspaces and actually touched special objects.

Discussion

This study introduced the scientific study of valued possessions in workplace environments. Although the current project did not meet its objectives of beginning the process of developing tools to measure employee affect using material in the physical environment, it is a significant step to the examination of symbolic communication in the workplace and employee affect. Analysis of interview data indicated the richness of the interview data as well as a relationship between interactions with special objects in the workplace and positive affect, which in turn has been linked to superior knowledge worker performance (Isen, 2001). The important influence of positive affect on knowledge worker attitudes and behaviors indicates that employer efforts to maximize employee interactions with their special objects will be rewarded with improved employee performance and well-being.

The failure to show a relationship in the survey data between any of the aspects of special objects and job satisfaction or organizational commitment, when coupled with the interview data analyses, adds strength to other research findings indicating separate affective and cognitive components of job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Thoresen et al., 2003). Although Thoresen et al.'s completed meta-analysis supported their hypotheses positively linking positive affect and both job satisfaction and organizational commitment, further analyses lead these researchers to state that "The moderate multiple correlations obtained for job satisfaction and organizational commitment are consistent with arguments that these constructs represent a mix of people's cognitive evaluations and affective reactions to job situations" (Thoresen et al., 2003, p. 933). Isen and Baron voice a similar opinion (1991). The fact that Wells (2000) and BOSTI (1984) observed a relationship between workplace personalization and job satisfaction, suggests that workplace personalization

behaviors may also share the affective/cognitive dichotomy present in the job satisfaction and organizational commitment measures.

These apparent affective/cognitive dualities increase the value of a tool to assess the affective state of an employee, potentially via relationships with valued possessions, because of the close ties between affect and action (such as resigning from a job); these ties can be particularly important when cognitively imposed constraints on actions are modified (Cote, 1999). Previous researchers have suggested that affective state might be a better predictor of worker performance than job satisfaction (Cote, 1999; Isen and Baron, 1991).

Workplace environments should support the positive emotional experiences that can result from the presentation of special objects. It is clear that the individuals interviewed would have had reduced positive affect if they were not able to position their special objects around themselves. Workplaces that maximize positive affect while minimizing negative affect should allow the display and ready access to objects viewed as special by individual employees. They should also allow objects that are inconsistent with self-concept to be shielded from view and other sorts of ready access to minimize negative affect. Workplaces should be designed to accommodate the variety of materials categorized as special by individuals. In addition, special objects should be clearly visible to new employees and visitors so that accurate interpretations of others can be made and so that workplace display norms can be easily learned. These design objectives will not be easy to achieve. Social mores should allow special object displays to be uninhibited.

Conclusions

Workspace designers must understand that they will not be the final generative force to act on optimal spaces. Fundamental psychological forces, such as the users' drives to present their self-concepts, will influence the final form of successful workplaces. Although special objects alone cannot determine that knowledge workers will experience positive affect, designers must create spaces that allow a range of different special objects to be presented, more public and less public displays of objects, and evolution of self-presentations over time.

This project indicates the potential value of descriptive research, in both more and less traditional (e.g., hoteling) workplaces, as well as the value of developing more sophisticated

tools to assess the effectiveness of different strategies to present special objects and to measure emotional responses at both the individual and group levels. Future research must investigate the nuances of emotional experiences different environments and objects can create, as well as how these spaces and objects can influence related factors such as place and artifact attachment, cross-cultural differences in emotional response, multi-sensory projections of the self, and differential responses to analogous objects and place designs in varied environments, such as retail and office spaces. Designers and social scientists must work together to create optimal spaces, because not only are fundamental human emotional forces in play during use of spaces, but also crucial design factors, such as appropriate levels of visual complexity.

Workspaces should allow emotion based expression and registration of that expression by others. Creating the optimal affective environment in workplaces will result in desirable worker attitudes and behaviors; just as creating the optimal affective environment in a retail setting results in desirable shopper attitudes and behaviors (Donovan & Rossiter, 1982).

References

- Balzar, W. K., Kihm, J. A., Smith, P. C., Irwin, J. L., Bachiochi, P. D., Robie, C., Sinar, E. F., and Parra, L. F. (1997) *Users' Manual for the Job Descriptive Index (JDI; 1997 Revision) and the Job in General (JIG) Scales*. Bowling Green, OH: Bowling Green State University.
- Baron, R. (1990) "Environmentally Induced Positive Affect: Its Impact on Self-Efficacy, Task Performance, Negotiation, and Conflict." *Journal of Applied Social Psychology* 20(5): 368-384.
- Becker, F. (1982) *The Successful Office*. Menlo Park, CA: Addison-Wesley.
- Belk, R. W. (1988) "Possessions and the Extended Self." *Journal of Consumer Research* 15(2): 139-168.
- Berger, P. and Luckmann, T. (1967) *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*. New York, NY: Penguin.
- Blumer, H. (1969) *Symbolic Interactionism: Perspective and Method*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- BOSTI. (1984) *The Impact of Office Environment on Productivity and Quality of Working Life*. Buffalo, NY: Buffalo Organization for Social and Technological Innovation.
- Brief, A. and Weiss. H. (2002) "Organizational Behavior: Affect in the Workplace." In Fiske, S., Schacter, D., and Zahn-Waxler, C. (eds) *Annual Review of Psychology, Volume 53*. Palo Alto, CA: Annual Reviews, 279-307.
- Burke, M., Brief, A., George, J., Roberson, L., and Webster, J. (1989) "Measuring Affect at Work: Confirmatory Analyses of Competing Mood Structures with Conceptual Linkage to Cortical Regulatory Systems." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 57(6): 1091-1102.

Cohen, J. (1960) "A Coefficient of Agreement for Nominal Scales." *Educational and Psychological Measurement* 20(1): 37-46.

Cote, S. (1999) "Affect and Performance in Organizational Settings." *Current Directions in Psychological Science* 8(2): 65-68.

Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1993) *The Evolving Self: A Psychology for the Third Millennium*. New York, NY: HarperCollins.

Csikszentmihalyi, M. and Rochberg-Halton, E. (1981) *The Meaning of Things: Domestic Symbols and the Self*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.

Dittmar, H. (1989) "Gender Identity-Related Meanings of Personal Possessions." *British Journal of Social Psychology* 28(6): 159-171.

Dittmar, H. (1992) *The Social Psychology of Material Possessions: To Have Is To Be*. New York, NY: St. Martin's.

Erez, M. and Earley, P.C. (1993) *Culture, Self-Identity, and Work*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

Donovan, R. and Rossiter, J. (1982) "Store Atmosphere: An Environmental Psychology Approach." *Journal of Retailing* 58(Spring): 34-57.

Fredrickson, B. (2001) "The Role of Positive Emotions in Positive Psychology." *American Psychologist* 56(3): 218-226.

Fredrickson, B. and Branigan, C. (2005) "Positive Emotions Broaden the Scope of Attention and Thought-Action Repertoires." *Cognition and Emotion* 19(3): 313-332.

Gagliardi, P. (1996) "Exploring the Aesthetic Side of Organizational Life." In Clegg, S., Hardy, C. and Nord, W. (eds) *Handbook of Organization Studies*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 565-580.

George, J. and Brief, A. (1992) "Feeling Good – Doing Good: A Conceptual Analysis of the Mood at Work – Organizational Spontaneity Relationship." *Psychological Bulletin* 112(2): 310-329.

Gorowara-Bhat, G. (2000) *The Social and Spatial Ecology of Work: A Case of a Survey Research Organization*. New York, NY: Kluwer Academic/Plenum.

Hackett, R. (1994) "Further Assessments of Meyer and Allen's 1991 Three-Component Model of Organizational Commitment." *Journal of Applied Psychology* 79(1): 15-23.

Hansen, W.B. and Altman, I. (1976) "Decorating Personal Places: A Descriptive Analysis." *Environment and Behavior* 8(4): 491-505.

Horne, S. C. (1997) "The Classroom Environment and the Effects on the Practice of Teachers." Unpublished paper, personal communication.

Isen, A. (2001) "An Influence of Positive Affect on Decision Making in Complex Situations: Theoretical Issues with Practical Implications." *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 11(2): 75-85.

Isen, A. and Baron, R. (1991) "Positive Affect as a Factor in Organizational Behavior." In Staw, B. and Cummings, L. (eds) *Research in Organizational Behavior, Volume 13*. Greenwich, CT: JAI Press, 1-53.

Isen, A., Johnson M., Mertz, E., and Robinson, G. (1985) "The Influence of Positive Affect on the Usualness of Word Associations." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 48(6): 1413-1426

James, K., Brodersen, M., and Eisenberg, J. (2004) "Workplace Affect and Workplace Creativity: A Review and Preliminary Model." *Human Performance* 17(2): 169-194.

Johns, G. (1996) *Organizational Behavior: Understanding and Managing Life at Work*. New York, NY: Harper Collins.

- Kamptner, N. L. (1991) "Personal Possessions and Their Meanings: A Life-Span Perspective." *Journal of Social Behavior and Personality* 6(6): 209-228.
- Locke, E. (1976) "The Nature and Causes of Job Satisfaction." In Dunnette, M. (ed) *Handbook of Individual and Organizational Psychology*. Chicago, IL: Rand McNally, 1297-1345.
- Loken, B. (2006) "Consumer Psychology: Categorization, Inferences, Affect, and Persuasion." In Fiske, S., Schacter, D., and Zahn-Waxler, C. (eds) *Annual Review of Psychology, Volume 57*. Palo Alto, CA: Annual Reviews, 453-485.
- Lunt, P.K. and Livingstone, S.M. (1992) *Mass Consumption and Personal Identity: Everyday Economic Experience*. Philadelphia, PA: Open University Press.
- Marcus, C. C. (1995) *House as a Mirror of Self: Exploring the Deeper Meaning of Home*. Berkeley, CA: Conari
- McCarthy, E. D. (1984) "Toward a Sociology of the Physical World: George Herbert Mead on Physical Objects." In Denzin, N. (ed) *Studies in Symbolic Interaction, 5*. Greenwich, CT: JAI Press, 105-121.
- Mowday, R. T., Porter, L. W., and Steers, R. M. (1982) *Employee-Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism, and Turnover*. New York, NY: Academic Press.
- Nippert-Eng. C. (1996) *Home and Work*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Richins, M. L. (1994) "Valuing Things: The Public and Private Meanings of Possessions." *Journal of Consumer Research* 21(3): 504-521.
- Rosenberg, M. (1986) *Conceiving the Self*. Malabar, FL: Krieger
- Scheiberg, S. L. (1990) "Emotions on Display: The Personal Decoration of Work Spaces." *American Behavioral Scientist* 33(3): 330-338.

Schein, E. (1992) *Organizational Culture and Leadership*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.

Sommer, R. (1974) *Tight Spaces: Hard Architecture and How to Humanize It*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.

Sundstrom, E. (1986) *Work Places: The Psychology of the Physical Environment in Office and Factories*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.

Tabachnick, B. and Fidell, L. (1996) *Using Multivariate Statistics, Third Edition*. New York, NY: Harper Collins College Publishers.

Thoresen, C., Kaplan, S., Barsky, A., and Warren, C. (2003) "The Affective Underpinnings of Job Perceptions and Attitudes: A Meta-Analytical Review and Integration." *Psychological Bulletin* 129(6): 914 – 945.

Vinsel, A., Brown, B., Altman, I., and Foss, C. (1980) "Privacy Regulation, Territorial Displays, and Effectiveness of Individual Functioning." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 39(7): 1104-1115.

Watson, D., Clark, L., and Tellegen, A. (1988) "Development and Validation of Brief Measures of Positive and Negative Affect: The PANAS Scales." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 54(6): 1063-1070.

Wells, M. (2000) "Office Clutter or Meaningful Personal Displays: The Role of Office Personalization in Employee and Organizational Well-Being." *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 20(3): 239-255.

Wilson, M. A. and MacKenzie, N.E. (2000) "Social Attributions Based on Domestic Interiors." *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 20(4): 343-354.